

Techno-Economic Analysis of Bio-Waste Valorization for Hydrogen Production using Supercritical Water Reforming Technology

Project developed by
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Description:

This project provides an in-depth techno-economic analysis (TEA) of a bio-based waste valorization plant that uses supercritical water reforming (SCWR) technology to convert bio-based glycerol, a byproduct of biodiesel production, into hydrogen (Figs 1 and 2). The analysis covers glycerol waste valorization using SCWR technology, the technical process, economic feasibility, and the potential industrial and domestic applications of hydrogen.

Objectives:

- 1) **To Evaluate Glycerol Production and Availability:** Analyze literature data from biodiesel production to quantify the availability of glycerol byproduct, leveraging research by Khalil (2021) and Ciriminna et al. (2014).
- 2) **To Assess the Economic Feasibility of using SCWR Technology:** Determine the cost-effectiveness and potential savings of converting glycerol into hydrogen compared to other methods such as direct steam reforming (SR) and advanced supercritical water reforming (ASCWR).
- 3) **To Design and Simulate a SCWR Plant for Efficient Hydrogen Production:** Develop a plant process design and use Aspen HYSYS to simulate the plant for hydrogen yield from glycerol as the feedstock.
- 4) **To Highlight the Economic and Environmental Benefits of this Waste Valorization Technology:** Perform plant economics analysis and calculate the cost of hydrogen production (in \$/kg) from this waste valorization technology. Also, discuss how hydrogen production from bio-waste can support sustainability goals, including reducing carbon emissions and adding economic value to biodiesel production processes.

Fig. 1. Flow diagram for bio-based waste to clean energy.

Fig. 2. System boundary of the Gradle-to-Gate hydrogen production plant.

References

Khalil, Y.F. (2021). Simulation-based environmental-impact assessment of glycerol-to-hydrogen conversion technologies. *Clean Energy*, Oxford University Press, 387–402.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/ce/zkab018>

Ciriminna et al. (2014). Understanding the glycerol market. *European Journal of Lipid Science and Technology*, 2014, 116(10):1432–1439.